

AiChemist Data Management Plan

Version 1

Description

Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Horizon Europe MSCA "Explainable AI for Molecules - AiChemist". This plan defines which kind of data will be generated and used by AiChemist Doctoral Candidates (DCs), how public and proprietary data will be handled, which types of data can be made available to the public, where the data will be published and under what circumstances. As the DCs progress in their individual research projects, the DMP will be updated and will go into more detail on standards for storing data, reusability and interoperability, and individual datasets and models will be described in the DMP.

Which data can be made publicly available?

Each DC, in consultation with their supervisors, is responsible for making their developed models and the respective data publicly available upon publication of results, as long as (1) the source data is already publicly available or (2) in cases where proprietary data is used, the company that owns the data allows said data to be published.

Purchased data (e.g. from Reaxys) and data linked to patents and IP cannot be made publicly available.

How should data be made publicly available?

Datasets and models related to publications will be made available on GitHub and/or Huggingface.

Best practices defined by GitHub/Huggingface will be used to make the data/models findable. Each repository will feature a comprehensive description of data, models, nomenclature and file structure in the README/Model Card, and will incorporate appropriate keywords into the README/Model Card.

<https://docs.github.com/en/contributing/writing-for-github-docs/making-content-findable-in-search>. <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/model-cards>.

For longer-term storage of data/models, Zotero will be used.

Public data related to molecular properties, activities or toxicities, will be stored in OCHEM <https://ochem.eu/>. Every student working on molecular property and/or activity prediction is responsible for uploading their data/models to OCHEM.

How should data be stored?

Each DC will store their data on their company/institutional hardware and will regularly make back-ups according to their company/institutional policy.

Contact

The project manager, Katya Ahmad, is responsible for monitoring compliance to FAIR data principles, updating the DMP, and answering any questions related to data management within the AiChemist Project.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Explainable AI for Molecules -
AiChemist
(corda_____he::101120466)

Researchers

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Organizations

Bayer (Germany), Technical University Eindhoven, AstraZeneca (Sweden), Barcelona University, Barcelona, Spain, Pfizer (Germany), Universiteit Leiden, Molecular Networks (Germany),

Universita della Svizzera Italiana, Helmholtz Zentrum München,
Ecole Polytechnique Fédéral de Lausanne, Ecole Normale
supérieure de Paris, Technische Universität München, Centre for
Genomic Regulation, University of Copenhagen, Sanofi (France),
Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS (IRFMN)

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: AiChemist Data Management Plan

Description:

Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Horizon Europe MSCA "Explainable AI for Molecules - AiChemist". This plan defines which kind of data will be generated and used by AiChemist Doctoral Candidates (DCs), how public and proprietary data will be handled, which types of data can be made available to the public, where the data will be published and under what circumstances. As the DCs progress in their individual research projects, the DMP will be updated and will go into more detail on standards for storing data, reusability and interoperability, and individual datasets and models will be described in the DMP.

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<https://docs.github.com/en/contributing/writing-for-github-docs/making-content-findable-in-search>. <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/model-cards>.

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Public data related to molecular properties, activities or toxicities, will be stored in OCHEM <https://ochem.eu/>. Every student working on molecular property and/or activity prediction is responsible for uploading their data/models to OCHEM.

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Each DC will store their data on their company/institutional hardware and will regularly make back-ups according to their company/institutional policy.

Contact

The project manager, Katya Ahmad, is responsible for monitoring compliance to FAIR data principles, updating the DMP, and answering any questions related to data management within the AiChemist Project.

Researchers:

[Karoline Schjelde \(orcid:0009-0002-7381-3435\)](https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7381-3435)

[Dina Khasanova \(orcid:0009-0003-7477-7664\)](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7477-7664)

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Marcel Hiltcher (orcid:0009-0001-6096-3584)
Matthew Ball (orcid:0009-0008-8777-1778)

Organizations:

Bayer (Germany)
Technical University Eindhoven
AstraZeneca (Sweden)
Barcelona University, Barcelona, Spain
Pfizer (Germany)
Universiteit Leiden
Molecular Networks (Germany)
Universita della Svizzera Italiana
Helmholtz Zentrum München
Ecole Polytechnique Fédéral de Lausanne
Ecole Normale supérieure de Paris
Technische Universität München
Centre for Genomic Regulation
University of Copenhagen
Sanofi (France)
Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS (IRFMN)

Contact: Ahmad Katya Ahmad (katya.ahmad@helmholtz-munich.de)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Explainable AI for Molecules - AiChemist (corda_____he::101120466)

Project:

3. License

License: MIT

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Personalized Cardiotoxicity Datasets

The dataset is derived from the FAERS pharmacovigilance database and includes drug-adverse event reports mapped to active ingredients and SMILES strings. Cardiotoxicity labels were assigned using disproportionality analysis metrics (ROR, PRR, IC) based on selected MedDRA terms. Demographic factors (sex, age, weight) were incorporated through stratified subsets. Multiple dataset versions were created to reflect variations in inclusion criteria and labeling methods. Label certainty scores are provided for use as sample weights in modeling. Dataset sizes range from ~2,000 to ~40,000 entries.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Iwan, Mateusz	0000-0001-5151-4659	mateusz.iwan@hotmail.com	Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Iwan, Mateusz	0000-0001-5151-4659	mateusz.iwan@hotmail.com	Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research	Creator
Roncaglioni, Alessandra	0000-0002-1734-0939	alessandra.roncaglioni@marionegri.it	Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research	Project member
Garcia de Lomana, Marina	0000-0002-9310-7290	marina.garciadelomana@bayer.com	Bayer AG	Project member
Grisoni, Francesca	0000-0001-8552-6615	f.grisoni@tue.nl	Eindhoven University of Technology	Project member

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

- a. Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS
- b. Bayer AG
- c. Eindhoven University of Technology

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

As the dataset has already been collected, cleaned, and curated, no additional financial costs are expected for data collection or processing. Time resources were primarily dedicated during the data preparation phase, including standardization,

labeling, and developing different versions of the dataset. The final datasets will be hosted on the OCHEM platform and Zenodo, which ensures persistent identifiers, standardized metadata, and long-term accessibility. A detailed documentation on the development will be provided to ensure reusability.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.1 Work package and task number

WP	Task
WP1: New representation learning methods	D1.1: Overview of molecular data

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

No

2.1.3 Creating a new dataset

To the best of our knowledge, no existing dataset combines cardiotoxicity information of drug-like molecules with demographic factors such as sex, age, and weight. Available pharmacovigilance datasets do not provide this integrated perspective, which is crucial for developing more personalized predictive models. Therefore, we have prepared a new dataset, derived from an already existing database (FAERS), to address these gaps. To make it easier to develop machine learning models, structural information is included in the dataset in the form of SMILES strings.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

AiChemist. WP1. CARDEM

2.2.2 Data types

- a. Numerical: continuous and discrete values representing statistical metrics and confidence-related scores from DPA
- b. Categorical: categories for demographic factors (Sex, Age, Weight), stratification type, and compound labels
- c. Binary (numerical): binary labels for cardiotoxicity
- d. Derived: the dataset was derived from the FAERS database
- e. Processed: Data has undergone cleaning, filtering, mapping, and is use-ready
- f. Digital: all data were generated and processed digitally

2.2.3 Data formats

- a. CSV: the finalized datasets will be provided as CSV file and available on OCHEM and Zenodo
- b. PDF: the associated paper or the description of preparation
- c. PKL: intermediate files
- d. PARQUET: raw file exported from MySQL database

2.2.4 Size of data

gigabytes (GB)

Comment:

A single variation of the finalized version of the dataset is around 4 MB, for a total of approximately 80 MB.

The raw data weight 1.7 GB. The intermediate files take approximately 60 GBs of space.

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The primary data source used in this project is the FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS), which is publicly available at: <https://fis.fda.gov/extensions/FPD-QDE-FAERS/FPD-QDE-FAERS.html>. FAERS contains reports on adverse drug reactions (ADRs) submitted by healthcare professionals, manufacturers, and patients. From this database, we extracted patient-level data (age, sex, weight) and drug-event associations. Cardiotoxic events were identified using MedDRA Preferred Terms. Raw drug names were standardized using a combination of synonym dictionaries and web-scraping heuristics, and then mapped to their corresponding active ingredients. Structural data in the form of SMILES strings was retrieved for each unique compound using public chemical databases.

Data provenance is tracked throughout the pipeline using version-controlled scripts. All data transformations—including drug name normalization, demographic binning, event filtering, and DPA calculations—are logged in reproducible Jupyter notebooks and Python scripts. The full codebase will be made publicly available on GitHub at:

<https://github.com/M-Iwan/#> (link placeholder; final URL will be provided upon publication)

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

The data were generated to develop and validate predictive models for drug-induced cardiotoxicity, incorporating demographic factors such as sex, age, and weight to improve personalized risk assessment. This dataset supports the project's goal of advancing machine learning approaches in pharmacovigilance. Beyond the project, the data can be used by researchers in drug safety, cheminformatics, and personalized medicine to enhance adverse event prediction, facilitate regulatory assessments, and guide safer drug design.

2.2.7 Dataset description

We used the FAERS database, which included data on 17.6 million patients, as our primary source. Raw drug descriptions were standardized and tokenized, and then

mapped to active ingredients (represented using SMILES strings) using synonym dictionaries and web-scraping heuristics. Patients' age was binned into four categories, following FDA age classification; weight was grouped into three bins based on sub-population distributions; and sex was used as-is. Cardiotoxic reactions were defined using MedDRA Preferred Terms.

We used Disproportionality Analysis (DPA) methods to identify drug-ADR pairs that occur more frequently than expected. Three popular DPA metrics – along with their confidence intervals (CIs) – were used to quantify cardiotoxic associations: Proportional Reporting Ratio (PRR), Reporting Odds Ratio (ROR), and Information component (IC). To reflect the strength of evidence for each label, we computed a confidence score based on the metric's distance to its threshold, normalized by CI width. These scores were then transformed using a modified sigmoid function and used as sample weights in training.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

The finalized dataset will be stored and made accessible via OCHEM, which supports standardized chemical data formats and persistent identifiers. A

versioned snapshot of the dataset will also be deposited on Zenodo to ensure long-term preservation and citation via DOI. The complete processing pipeline and source code will be made available on GitHub, enabling full reproducibility. Due to storage constraints, raw and intermediate data files will not be preserved long-term; however, they can be regenerated using the published scripts and metadata.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
OCHEM (Online Chemical Database with Modeling Environment)	https://ochem.eu	Yes	No	Discipline specific
GitHub	https://github.com	No	Yes	Discipline specific
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org	Yes	Yes	Generalist

4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

For the dataset, long-term preservation will be ensured by depositing it on the OCHEM platform, a widely used domain-specific repository for cheminformatics and predictive modeling. OCHEM provides persistent identifiers, supports standardized metadata, and guarantees continued availability of public datasets, which aligns well with FAIR principles.

For the software, all code and relevant documentation will be hosted on GitHub. To ensure long-term access and reproducibility, a snapshot of the final version of the repository will be archived using Zenodo, which mints a DOI and preserves both the code and its metadata. This integration enables both version tracking (via

GitHub) and long-term preservation (via Zenodo), making the codebase citable and reusable.

No non-digital objects are involved in this project.

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
Not yet available.	Not yet available.

Comment:

Not yet available.

4.2.2 Metadata

The dataset will be accompanied by rich metadata to support discovery, understanding, and reuse. Metadata will be provided at multiple levels:

- Zenodo: A versioned snapshot of the dataset will be deposited in Zenodo, which uses the DataCite metadata schema and assigns a DOI. This includes title, creators, description, keywords, license, related publications, and versioning.

- OCHEM: Metadata in OCHEM will include chemical identifiers (e.g., SMILES), compound names, and structured annotations using standard ontologies where applicable.

- GitHub Repository: The code repository will contain a detailed readme.txt file describing the dataset generation process, feature definitions, dependencies, and

instructions for reproduction.

- Paper: A peer-reviewed publication will serve as an authoritative reference, providing a comprehensive description of data sources, processing pipeline, quality checks, and intended use cases.

Additional plain-text documentation may be included alongside downloadable datasets.

4.2.3 Keywords

Pharmacovigilance,Cardiotoxicity,Disproportionality Analysis,Machine Learning, FAERS,QSAR

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The finalized version of the dataset will be made publicly available through the OCHEM platform, ensuring long-term accessibility and integration with cheminformatics tools. In addition, a versioned archive of the dataset will be deposited on Zenodo, which will assign a persistent DOI and support standardized metadata for citation and discovery. Metadata and supporting documentation will be provided either directly on the OCHEM page or via a public GitHub repository that also hosts the associated code and preprocessing pipeline. This setup will ensure that users can easily access, understand, and reuse the dataset.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

The dataset was prepared using a standardized pipeline to ensure interoperability. Drug data were mapped to active ingredients using open chemical databases (e.g., ChEMBL, PubChem), and structural information was represented via SMILES strings. Labels were derived using established Disproportionality Analysis metrics

(e.g., IC, ROR, PRR) and standardized MedDRA Preferred Terms. Demographic attributes were harmonized into predefined categories (e.g., Sex, Age groups, Weight classes). Data processing was conducted using widely adopted tools such as Python (pandas, RDKit, NumPy), ensuring reproducibility and compatibility. The dataset is stored in open formats (CSV), enabling easy integration with other systems and tools.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

The dataset leverages several established vocabularies and standards to ensure semantic interoperability and facilitate reuse:

- MedDRA (Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities): Used for the definition and grouping of cardiotoxicity-related adverse events through standardized Preferred Terms (PTs), ensuring consistent labeling across pharmacovigilance studies.
- SMILES: Structural chemical information is encoded using SMILES notation, a widely adopted standard in cheminformatics.
- FAERS standard fields: Original source data adheres to FDA FAERS schema and controlled vocabularies.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

4.5.2 Documentation

The dataset will be accompanied by a full peer-reviewed publication that describes the data preparation, processing steps, labeling methodology, and model development in detail. Additionally, a README file will be included with the dataset to summarize its structure, content, and usage instructions. All relevant code will be made available via a public GitHub repository to ensure full transparency and reproducibility.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Several measures were implemented to ensure the consistency and quality of the dataset:

- Standardized data processing pipeline: All data were processed using reproducible Python scripts with strict validation checks at each stage (e.g., mapping, cleaning, labeling).
- Use of controlled vocabularies: Drug names, adverse events, and demographic attributes were normalized using established vocabularies such as MedDRA and standardized chemical identifiers (SMILES).
- Manual inspection: Sample subsets were manually inspected during critical steps (e.g., mapping drugs to active ingredients) to ensure accuracy.
- Version control: All code and data transformations are tracked using version control (Git), enabling full traceability and reproducibility.
- Cross-checking label consistency: Disproportionality analysis results were verified using multiple metrics (IC, ROR, PRR), and label confidence was calculated to highlight uncertain cases.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Local Hard Drive (PC, laptop)

Comment:

During the active phase of the research, all data were stored locally on two dedicated, access-controlled PCs. Code and data processing scripts were version-controlled and collaboratively managed via GitHub. To ensure redundancy and data security, key datasets and essential intermediate files were also backed up to two separate cloud storage services. These backups were sufficient to fully reconstruct the final dataset. Access to local and cloud resources was restricted to authorized team members and managed internally.

5.2.2 Backup

During the research, intermediate files and processed datasets were regularly backed up to cloud storage platforms (Dropbox and Google Drive).

Access to all storage locations—both local and online—was restricted to authorized project team members. In the event of data loss or corruption, files could be recovered from the most recent cloud backup or reconstructed from GitHub and preserved intermediate data.

5.2.3 Additional security

The dataset does not contain any sensitive, personal, or proprietary information. All records are fully anonymized and derived from publicly available pharmacovigilance sources, primarily the FDA FAERS database. Given the non-sensitive nature of the data, no additional security measures beyond standard data protection, controlled access during the active research phase, and regular backups were deemed necessary.

Benchmark datasets molecular property prediction

These datasets were used to benchmark representation learning methods based on their performance in tasks relevant to drug discovery. The datasets were collected from established platforms that curate benchmark datasets for machine learning applications in drug discovery and were subsequently cleaned and standardized to enhance their overall quality, coherence, and usability.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Krüger Fabian	0009-0005-6420-2175	fabian.krueger@tum.de	Technische Universität München, Helmholtz Munich, AstraZeneca

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Krüger, Fabian	0009-0005-6420-2175	fabian.krueger@tum.de	Technische Universität München,	Creator

			Helmholtz Munich, AstraZeneca	
Tetko, Igor	0000-0002- 6855-0012	itetko@ai-dd.eu	Helmholtz Munich	Supervisor
Engkvist, Ola	0000-0003- 4970-6461	Ola.Engkvist@a strazeneca.com	AstraZeneca	Supervisor

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

- a. Technische Universität München (TUM)
- b. AstraZeneca AB
- c. Helmholtz Munich

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

N/A. The data and all methods of preparing it are published in an open access scientific journal article. Thus, all the costs for maintained public access are already paid

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.1 Work package and task number

WP	Task
1	1

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

Yes

2.1.2 Re-using an existing dataset: why and how

We made a collection of publicly available datasets to benchmark representation learning methods across a range of different tasks. We cleaned the data to ensure the data is standardized across tasks.

All datasets we have collected are licensed for free reuse and re-distribution, therefore we do not have any potential restrictions to data re-use

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

Ames, BBB, hERG, DEL

2.2.2 Data types

- a. quantitative
- b. processed
- c. text to scalar

2.2.3 Data formats

comma separated values

2.2.4 Size of data

kilobytes (KB)

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

We used four different datasets to predict pharmacologically relevant molecular properties. The datasets differ in size, task, and class imbalance. The first dataset is used for mutagenicity prediction [18, 19]. It contains Ames test results for 7,255 drugs. Of these, 54% show positive results. The second dataset assesses blood-brain barrier permeability [17]. It contains 1,909 molecules, with 76% able to

penetrate the barrier. The third dataset provides information on the inhibition of the potassium ion channel encoded by the human Ether-à-go-go-Related Gene (hERG) [21]. Inhibition is defined as a half-maximal inhibitory concentration of less than 10

M. This dataset contains 306,341 compounds, with 4.5% being inhibitors. These three datasets were obtained from Therapeutics Data Commons [22]. The fourth dataset contains information on whether a molecule is enriched in a DNA-encoded library (DEL) for binding to carbonic anhydrase IX [20]. Positive enrichment is defined as the top 5% of enrichment scores. This dataset includes 108,528 molecules, with 4.9% showing enrichment after cleaning the data.

17 Martins Ines Filipa, Teixeira Ana L, Pinheiro Luis, Falcao Andre O (2012) A bayesian approach to in silico blood-brain barrier penetration modeling. *J Chem Inf Model* 52(6):1686–1697

18 Hansen Katja, Mika Sebastian, Schroeter Timon, Sutter Andreas, Ter Laak Antonius, Steger-Hartmann Thomas, Heinrich Nikolaus, Muller Klaus-Robert (2009) Benchmark data set for in silico prediction of ames mutagenicity. *J Chem Inf Model* 49(9):2077–2081

19 Congying Xu, Cheng Feixiong, Chen Lei, Zheng Du, Li Weihua, Liu Guixia, Lee Philip W, Tang Yun (2012) In silico prediction of chemical ames mutagenicity. *J Chem Inf Model* 52(11):2840–2847

20 Lim Katherine S, Reidenbach Andrew G, Hua Bruce K, Mason Jeremy W, Gerry Christopher J, Clemons Paul A, Coley Connor W (2022) Machine learning on dna-encoded library count data using an uncertainty-aware probabilistic loss function. *J Chem Inf Model* 62(10):2316–2331

21 Fang Du, Haibo Yu, Zou Beiyan, Babcock Joseph, Long Shunyou, Li Min (2011) Hergcentral: a large database to store, retrieve, and analyze compound-human ether-a-go-go related gene channel interactions to facilitate cardiotoxicity assessment in drug development. *Assay Drug Dev Technol* 9(6):580–588

22 Huang Kexin, Tianfan Fu, Gao Wenhao, Zhao Yue, Roohani Yusuf, Leskovec Jure, Coley Connor W, Xiao Cao, Sun Jimeng, Zitnik Marinka (2021) Therapeutics data commons: Machine learning datasets and tasks for drug discovery and development. arXiv preprint arXiv:2102.09548

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

We made a collection of publicly available datasets to benchmark representation learning methods across a range of different tasks (which is the objective of the project).

2.2.7 Dataset description

This collection includes 4 datasets that reflect a range of common tasks in drug discovery. All are binary classification data. The first dataset describes whether molecules pass the blood brain barrier, the second describes the results of the ames test, the third whether a molecule inhibits the hERG encoded potassium receptor, and the last one whether a molecule is enriched in a DNA-encoded library (DEL) for binding to carbonic anhydrase IX.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

The data is published together with the corresponding research article in Journal of Cheminformatics (open access article):

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-025-00982-w>

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
GitHub	https://github.com/FabianKruger/molprivacy	Yes	No	Generalist
Journal of Cheminformatics	https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-025-00982-w	Yes	No	Generalist

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-025-00982-w

4.2.2 Metadata

All the meta data is in the published research paper:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-025-00982-w>

4.2.3 Keywords

drug discovery, qsar

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

Click this link to access the article: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-025-00982-w>

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

Published to GitHub -> cloned by journal -> assigned doi -> published in open access article

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

We used the Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System to specify molecules in accordance with the gold standard in the field.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

MIT, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIT_License

Comment:

MIT License

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4.5.2 Documentation

Everything is in the open access paper:
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-025-00982-w>

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Peer review by journal:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-025-00982-w>

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Institutional internal Server

5.2.2 Backup

They are available on GitHub and in the journal itself. If one is lost, it can be restored from the other.

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